

Standardization of recipe for nutraceutical dark chocolate bar with added moringa and quinoa

^[1]Rohan R. Shah*

^[1] M. Tech (Food Technology) MIT ADT University
Pune, Maharashtra, India

^[1] rohanshah19983107@gmail.com*

Abstract— The purpose of this research project is to develop a nutraceutical, chocolate based confectionary product which will provide benefits other than that of traditional chocolate. We felt like there is a need to produce some innovative confection other than traditional chocolates. The nutraceutical chocolate bar which we have manufactured is more nutritious and healthier due to its rare ingredients which also makes it a unique nutraceutical chocolate bar. The raw materials required for the preparation of this bar like moringa and quinoa along with fruits like kiwi, pineapple, apricots and nuts like almonds, cashew nuts, peanuts and desiccated coconut are procured from market. For the standardization of formulation, 4 test samples were prepared of different proportions of raw materials, among which the T4 was selected by sensory panelist based on organoleptic evaluation. The bar is further packed into the aluminum foil wrappers. The approximate nutritional values obtained by analysis are particularly as, Protein 5.19 gm, Fat 29.15 gm, Carbohydrate 37.28 gm Fiber 22.8 gm. The storage conditions are studied at variable temperature conditions and recommended to be as below 200C in cool, dark and dry place. The well packed bars were studied for the duration of 3 month to determine its shelf life.

Index Terms— Confection, Innovative, Organoleptic, Nutraceutical.

I. INTRODUCTION

Developing a nutraceutical or functional food is becoming mandatory as looking at the current nutritional status of population over world. The nutraceutical foods are proven to cause several health benefits to the people. Hence the basic aim behind developing the nutraceutical chocolate bar was to fulfill the nutritional demands and provide some additional benefits to people. The product mainly contains two key ingredients that are, Drumstick (*Moringa oleifera*) which has most qualities to call it as a Superfood” and Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*) which is referred to as “Mother of all grains” This product also contains some fruits and nuts to make it taste delicious as well as nutritionally sound. The formulation of such chocolate bar containing bioactive components was relatively easy as it contains some miracle causing ingredients like moringa which has plenty of health benefits along with a grain like quinoa consisting of a wide amino acid profile and some fruits, nuts. Blending these ingredients caused a major change in overall nutritional profile of traditional chocolate and made it functional in several aspects. Hence such chocolate provides consumers something more than just the chocolate gives. Usually products and food preparation of scientifically proven beneficial effects on the human body are referred to as functional foods. Their action is to improve the health and well being, as well as reducing the risk of disease, especially the civilization once. (Vanda Rogavaska 2015)

Chocolates are typically sweet, usually brown, food preparation of *Theobroma cacao* seeds roasted and ground often flavored as with vanilla. Dark chocolate is also called as black chocolate is produced by adding fat and sugar to cocoa (K. Haritha 2014). Throughout history, chocolate has been used to treat a wide variety of ailments and in recent years, multiple studies have found that chocolate can have positive health effects providing evidence to a centuries- long established use (Donatella Lippi).

1. MATERIAL AND METHODS

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Select the clean, dry, dust free dry fruits and nuts. Sort and Grade them on the basis of size, shape and other quality parameters. Selected nuts are roasted at around 204 °C. Cut the fruits and nuts into small pieces. For peanuts, the husk is removed after roasting. Take and measure specific quantity of chocolate compound. Chocolate compound is chopped into uniform pieces to ensure even melting. Melt the chocolate to obtain required consistency. The chocolate is melted using double boiler method. Stir the chocolate with spatula and blend white, dark and milk chocolate properly. Now add moringa powder in previously prepared chocolate mixture. Add the chopped dry fruits and nuts into the blend. Mix all ingredients properly into the blend. The mixture is poured into the mould in specific quantity. Allow it to set for some time by keeping it in freezer. Remove the bar from mould after it gets solidified. The quinoa bar is ready for wrapping and packing. Wrap the bar in aluminium foil chocolate wrapper.

- The procedure for preparing the nutraceutical chocolate bar is given fig. 1*

Select the clean, dry, dust free dry fruits and nuts. Sort and Grade them on the basis of size, shape and other quality parameters. Selected nuts are roasted at around 204 °C. Cut the fruits and nuts into small pieces. For peanuts, the husk is removed after roasting. Take and measure specific quantity of chocolate compound. Chocolate compound is chopped into uniform pieces to ensure even melting. Melt the chocolate to obtain required consistency. The chocolate is melted using double boiler method. Stir the chocolate with spatula and blend white, dark and milk chocolate properly. Now add moringa powder in previously prepared chocolate mixture. Add the chopped dry fruits and nuts into the blend. Mix all ingredients properly into the blend. The mixture is poured into the mould in specific quantity. Allow it to set for some time by keeping it in freezer. Remove the bar from mould after it gets solidified. The quinoa bar is ready for

wrapping and packing. Wrap the bar in aluminium foil chocolate wrapper.

- For optimization procedure Moringa Powder, Quinoa, Almonds, Cashew Nuts, Apricots, Peanuts, Dried Kiwi, Dried Pineapple, Desiccated Coconut, Dark, White and Milk chocolate compound were added to the blend of melted chocolate compounds in different proportions and combination.

- The prepared test sample was organoleptically evaluated by the sensory panel.

- On the organoleptic analysis the best test sample was selected as per the rating on hedonic scale for color, texture, flavor, and overall acceptability.

Part 1- Preparation of Raw Material

Part 2. Preparation of Quimo bar

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION STANDARDIZATION OF RECIPE

As per the sensory evaluation scores based on nine point hedonic scale the T4 sample (77.25% major components for

example- Dark, white and milk compound) and then 22.5% minor components. The test sample 1 got minimum score due to the bitter and unacceptable taste of moringa.

The test sample 2 and 3 were not liked by sensory panelist because it was over sweet and the color was less attractive as compared to T4 sample. Hence due to the higher overall acceptability of the T4 sample it was further used for storage and shelf life study.

A. Sensory analysis

The overall acceptability of the test sample 4 was decreased from the initial score of 8.5 to 8.3 at the end of product which is wrapped in aluminium foil and stored at temperature below 20°C for the period of 3 months. This might be due to the very slight moisture attained by the sample.

Sr. No	Sensory attributes	0 day	1 month	2 month	3 month
1	Color	8.5	8.5	8.5	8
2	Appearance	9	9	9	9
3	Texture	9	9	8.9	8.9
4	Taste	9	9	9	9
5	Flavor	9	9	9	9
6	Aroma	8	9	8.9	8.8
7	Mouth feel	8.5	8.7	9	9
8	Overall acceptability	9	8.8	8.9	8.8

Table No. 1 Sensory Analysis

Fig No-1 Sensory Analysis

B. Chemical analysis

Sr. No	Chemical Parameter	0 days	1 month	2 month	3 month
1	Moisture content	3.75 %	No Change	No change	4.05%
2	Ash	1.79 %	No Change	No Change	1.67%

Table No-2 Chemical Analysis

C. Moisture content

The moisture of the product is the major factor affecting its shelf life. The moisture content of sample was determined by AOAC 20th Ed 2016; Chapter no.4, Method no. 934.01. The T4 was properly wrapped in aluminum foil wrapper and initially detected to have the moisture content of 3.79% at 0 day. The sample was observed to have no changes at 1 month and two month. There was a slight change in the moisture content at about 4.05% which can be considered negligible. Humidity was a major factor affecting the moisture at the time of storage. Thus on the completion of 3 months of storage the final moisture was observed to be as 4.05% but it is still acceptable as it doesn't cause any other changes in the product.

D. Ash

Ash content resembles the total inorganic material which gradually decreases as the storage period of the food sample increases. The ash content was determined by AOAC 20th ED 2016; Chapter no.4, Method no. 942.05. The ash content was noted to be 1.79 % on 0 day analysis. Then sample was analysis in one month and 2nd month there has no change in ash and in 3rd month the ash content had slightly decreased to 1.67 % on storage.

Fig No-2 Chemical Analysis

E. Effects on nutritional parameters

The T4 was studied for proximate analysis at 0 day, 1 month, 2 month and 3 month.

F. Protein

The protein content in nutraceutical bar wrapped in aluminum foil is analyzed by AOAC 20th ED2016; Chapter no.4, Method no.954.01. The protein content was initially noted to be as 5.19 gm at 0 day. There were no specific changes observed in protein content at the end of 2nd and 3rd month. So it can be said that there is no effects on protein content at the end of 3rd month and it's noted to be as 5.19 gm.

G. Fat

The monosaccharide fat is a major factor which can possibly contribute in saying that the product is either healthy or unhealthy. The T4 was analyzed by AOAC 20th ED 2016; Chapter no.4, Method no. 954.01 at 0 day and observed for the results which is 29.15 gm, whereas, there were no changes occurred in fat during the span of 1 month and 2 month. Finally at the end of 3 month the fat was observed to be 30.10 gm showing no changes.

H. Carbohydrate

The carbohydrate was determined by FAO, Chapter no. 2, and Method no. 2.3. As per 0 day analysis of Test sample 4, the carbohydrate was observed to be as 37.28 gm per 100 gm of sample. When the same sample was analyzed at

1 month, 2 month and 3 month, the observed value for carbohydrate was constant as before stating 37.28 gm.

I. Fiber

The fiber content was determined by AOAC 20th ED 2016; Chapter no.4, Method no. 978.10. The fiber content was initially observed to be as 22.8 grams. There were no several changes observed in fiber content of nutraceutical chocolate bar during the storage of 2 months in well packed condition. At the end of 3 month, the fiber content was constant as 22.8 gm. But there was no assurance that this would not change on extended storage than that of 3 months.

Sr. No	Nutritional Parameter	0-3 month
1	Protein	5.1 gm
2	Fat	29.15 gm
3	Fiber	22.8 gm
4	Carbohydrate	37.28 gm

Table no.- Nutritional Parameter

Fig No-3 Nutritional Parameter

J. Physical analysis

Physical appearance is very important. The size of quimo bar is 4×8cm and the quimo bar is in rectangular shape. The texture shows gumminess, chewiness and cohesiveness.

Sr. No	Physical Parameter	Result
1	Size	4×8cm
2	Shape	Rectangular shape
3	Hardness	27.6 Kg.cm ⁻² @20°C
4	Texture	Cohesive ,Gummy, Chewy

Table No-4 Physical Analysis

K. Microbial analysis

Microbial safety of the food products is a major factor which may be responsible for causing some severe changes and effects in food products. Hence, the total plate count

was studied by means of spread plate technique. The T4 sample was stored for 3 months and same sample was used throughout the microbial analysis. As per the observations made on 0 day analysis, the colony count was 0.7×10² CFU/ mL while, looking towards the observations made on 1 month analysis the colony count was 1.2×10² CFU/ mL. Similarly, the observation for 2nd and 3rd month analysis are 1.4×10² CFU/ mL and 1.8×10² CFU/ mL respectively. Considering the microbial safety aspect of the chocolate bar, the results were under the recommended range and the product was microbial safe till the duration of 3 months.

Sr. No	Day / month	Colonies	Colony count unit (cfu/g)
1	0	07	0.7 x 10 ²
2	1	12	1.2 x 10 ²
3	2	14	1.4 x 10 ²
4	3	18	1.8 x 10 ²

Table No-5 Microbial Analysis

Fig No-4 Microbial Analysis

L. Storage study

The Test sample 4 was stored at variable temperature such as refrigeration temperature (1°C to 4°C), 10°C, 20°C, 30°C for the duration of 3 months. The sample stored at 30°C was observed to have visibly notable changes and it was unacceptable. Whereas, sample stored at 10°C to 20°C did not show any notable changes in any parameter. The sample stored at refrigeration temperature made it relatively hardened and also affected its results.

CONCLUSION

From the research study that we have conducted on this nutraceutical dark chocolate bar infused with moringa and quinoa, we concluded that this product is a highly nutritious product containing some traces of higher bio active compounds which can potentially provide several health benefits and also maintains the overall health. As per the storage study which was carried out for the duration of 3 months, the product did not show any objectionable changes and withstood at its best condition during overall shelf life

study. This bar have gone through several analytical

evaluations like sensory, chemical, physical and microbial in the duration of 3 months and on the basis of results, it is clear to say that, the product is absolutely safe for consumption till 3 months. The quality of the bar is not affected if it is well packed and stored under the recommended storage conditions as the result of this study.

REFERENCES

2. Maradini-Filho AM. (2017) Quinoa: Nutritional Aspects Food Journal of Nutraceuticals and Food Science vol.2 No. 1:3.
 3. Jancurová M., Minarovičová L., Dandár A. (2009): Quinoa – a review. Czech J. Food Sci., 27: 71-79.
 4. G Sandeep, T Anitha, KR Vijayalatha, A Sadasakthi, (2019) Moringa for nutritional security International Journal of Botany Studies (Moringa oleifera Lam.) Vol.4.
 5. Lia M. Nightingale, Keith R. Cadwallader and Nicki J. Engeseth (2012) Changes in dark chocolate volatiles during storage, J. Agric. Food Chem. 2012, 60, 18, 4500-4507.
 6. Ganatra Tejas H , Joshi Umang H, Bhalodia Payal N, Desai Tusharbindu R, Tirgar Pravin R, (2012) A PANORAMIC VIEW ON PHARMACOGNOSTIC, PHARMACOLOGICAL, NUTRITIONAL, THERAPEUTIC AND PROPHYLACTIC VALUES OF MORINGA OLEIFERA LAM, International Research Journal Of Pharmacy.
 7. Vanda Rogovska, Miroslava Čukanová (2015), Chocolate as a functional food.
 8. Ranganna, S., 1996, Handbook of analysis and quality control for fruits and vegetables products. Tata McGrew- Hill, Pub,Co.Ltd., New Delhi, pp. 84-86.
- M. chitkara, R. kohli, I. singhsandhu, D. singh(2016) Development and nutritional, organoleptic, biochemical analysis of polyherbal (stevia, banana, cocoa butter and oat)*
9. K. Haritha, L. Kalyani and A. Lakshmana Rao Health Benefits of Dark Chocolate, Journal of Advanced Drug Delivery 2014; 1(4); 184-195.
 10. R. Latif Chocolate/cocoa and human health: a review, The journal of medicine 2013, vol. 71, no 2.